

Cost of Nectar Research Cloud service if provided by commercial cloud

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Background

The aim of this activity was to estimate the cost of the cloud capacity provided to users by the Nectar Research Cloud if it had instead been provided through a commercial cloud service such as Amazon Web Services (AWS).

An estimate of the actual costs of cloud services for the Nectar cloud, and hence a direct comparison of the costs of Nectar vs AWS, will be done in future work.

Previous work

There have been a few previous analyses of the cost of Nectar cloud (or other on-prem infrastructure) vs commercial cloud:

- Nectar project estimate (2017)
- QCIF analysis of QRISCloud cost vs AWS (2017)
- [QCIF - ARDC Discovery Activity](#) (2019)
- [Garvan Institute - ARDC Discovery Activity](#) (2019)

Some other Nectar Nodes including Monash and Melbourne have also done analyses of their own costs vs commercial cloud at various times.

The results from this previous work have shown estimated costs for the Nectar cloud to be approximately 2-5 times less expensive than commercial cloud options, depending on the particular type of infrastructure or requirements.

Many studies have shown that for a large scale cloud with high base load usage, it is more cost effective to run a private OpenStack cloud than to use commercial cloud, with the cost difference increasing with scale. This is one of the main reasons why many large companies run their own in-house cloud infrastructure. The cost benefits are even larger if the use case requires large amounts of volume or block storage (as is the case for the Nectar cloud), which is very expensive on AWS, as opposed to object storage where Amazon S3 storage is relatively cheap.

A quick analysis done by Nectar in early 2017, looking just at compute costs (i.e. not including cloud storage), showed that the cost of provisioning the (then) 30,000 vCPUs in the Nectar cloud with equivalent Amazon virtual machine instances would be approximately \$10M per year, which was at least 50% higher than the total cost of the Nectar cloud, including the initial Nectar capex, Nectar operations costs, and Node co-investment for operations, even with very conservatively high costs for the Nectar cloud, e.g. including high initial setup costs of Nectar Nodes which wouldn't need to be repeated, and assuming only a four year equipment refresh cycle.

In late 2017 QCIF did a more detailed analysis of its own costs for Nectar vs Amazon, including storage, and then expanded this analysis to the whole of Nectar, and provided the information to the Nectar Platforms Steering Committee. Similar to the Nectar analysis, this analysis showed that even with conservatively high estimates of Nectar costs, the equivalent Amazon cost was at least 50% higher, and close to twice the cost if looking at equivalent storage performance.

Note that the cost difference for high-end infrastructure (GPU servers and large memory machines) is significantly greater than for generic cloud compute capacity, and there was much less high-end infrastructure in the Nectar cloud when these earlier estimates were done.

Methods

In this work the ARDC Core Services team used information about the usage of Nectar VMs and storage during the 2020/21 financial year and estimated the cost of provisioning the same capacity in the Nectar cloud.

Note that there are a lot of assumptions and approximations and caveats around this comparison because there is not a simple 1-1 mapping from Nectar services to AWS services, or Nectar VM flavors to AWS flavors.

We looked at two different approaches to estimating the cost of Nectar compute usage in AWS:

1. A simple approach just using total vcpu use, ignoring differences in flavors and RAM, and compared this to AWS costs for a generic AWS flavor
2. A more detailed approach mapping each Nectar flavor onto the most similar AWS flavor, and using usage information for each flavor to come up with a total cost, using a Jupyter notebook

The second approach is in principle more accurate but is much more complicated to implement and has problems with dealing with the many non-standard Nectar flavors that are used, mapping all these to AWS flavors would take too long. So we ended up using the first approach. We will adopt something more similar to the second approach in future work.

Both approaches assume the usage cost is based on AWS on-demand instances, since this is what Nectar provides to users. The closest standard AWS flavors to the Nectar standard flavors are:

- M5a flavors which are aimed at generic use and provide 1 vcpu per cpu thread
- T3a flavors which are more oversubscribed but burstable (aimed at bursty workloads)

Both are for AMD cpus (M5 and T3 are for Intel). Nectar flavors are somewhere in between these two options, but since the cost difference between the two is small (around 10%), it doesn't really matter which we choose. We were conservative and went with the lower price option of T3, and based the cost on the price for the Sydney AWS region. This equates to:

- AU\$0.0646 per vcpu-hour for t3a.large (4GB per vcpu)
- AU\$0.0323 per vcpu-hour for t3a.medium (2GB per vcpu)

Nectar standard flavors are 2GB per vcpu, RAM-optimised flavors are 4GB per vcpu, and there are Huge RAM and private flavors used by Nodes that provide much higher RAM per vcpu. On average the actual used RAM per vcpu for VMs running on Nectar is approximately 3.75, i.e. a little under 4GB per vcpu. So we use the figure for the t3a.large flavor of \$0.0646 per vcpu-hour.

AWS also allows users to reserve capacity for a particular time period (e.g. 1 year) and pay for that capacity whether they use it or not. This can be significantly cheaper, almost half the cost, and may be more cost-effective for some users and use cases. It would be very difficult to estimate the proportion of the usage of Nectar for which reserved instances would be more cost effective than on-demand instances.

AWS also offers spot (pre-emptible) instances, where the price varies on a spot market based on bids from users. These can be roughly a quarter of the price of on-demand instances, with the caveat that they can be shut down and given to other customers at any time. Nectar also offers spot instances but currently they are only a very small fraction of total usage.

Results

If we take the amount of usage on the Nectar cloud during their 2020/21 financial year, and estimate how much that would cost to provide on the Amazon commercial cloud (AWS), noting all these caveats and assumptions and choices outlined above, it is very approximately:

- \$25.9M for compute - 401M vcpu-hours @ \$0.0646 per vcpu-hour
- \$3.9M for volume storage - 3.4 PB at \$0.096 per GB-month
- \$0.3M for object storage - 1.0 PB and ~600GB/day transfer
- **\$30.1M total**

Note this estimate does not take into account:

- AWS costs for accessing/uploading/downloading data for volume storage which can be significant for some workloads.
- GPUs in the compute costs. The proportion of GPUs will significantly increase in 2021/22, and we will revise these estimates to include GPUs in future work.

- the level of user support that is provided by Nectar and the Node operators compared to what is offered by AWS
- other activities that ARDC needs to provide as part of NCRIS, including gathering and supporting specific user requirements, and reporting to the government (FoR codes, research grants, publications, etc).

The total cost of running the Nectar cloud is expected to be less than \$10M per year, so overall the cost of Nectar is estimated to be (very approximately, with a lot of caveats) at least 3 times less than using AWS. We will provide an improved estimate of equivalent AWS cost, and an estimate of the cost of the Nectar cloud, in future work. This work was not meant to provide a direct cost comparison of Nectar vs AWS, just to estimate the cost of running Nectar workloads in AWS.

Future Work

As part of the work in moving Nectar to usage-based quota, costs will be associated with the use of all different VM flavors, in both Service Units (basically vcpu-years) and a dollar figure which is based on an approximate cost for a similar flavor in AWS. This information is already being captured for current standard flavors but we still need to specify and capture this information for private flavors and GPUs. We are also still working on scripts for reporting usage (including the AWS equivalent cost estimate) at different levels - project, university, Node, and for the whole of Nectar. Once this is done we will be able to easily generate AWS-equivalent costs for Nectar usage for any specified time period. This work is expected to be completed in Q3 2022.

In the second half of 2022 we will start working on developing an estimate of costs for the Nectar cloud. This work will be needed in order to explore possibly moving to a cost subsidy model for Nectar cloud Nodes in future, as has previously been proposed. In 2015-16(?) the Nectar project hired a consultant to work with the Nodes to get approximate costs for providing the Nectar cloud service. These estimates varied widely between Nodes and it was difficult to come up with a standard estimate of the cost or provision of the Nectar service. There was some discussion about coming up with a standard price for the Nectar service for pay-for-use but the Steering Committee did not agree with implementing such a price. Costs, and some Nodes, have changed since that previous work.